

Advances and Challenges in Lensless Imaging and Sensing Technologies for Point-of-Care Biosensing

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Keywords: lensless imaging, Digital in-line holography, point-of-care diagnostics, biosensors, telemedicine

Abstract

Lensless imaging and sensing technology (LIST) has emerged as a powerful platform for point-of-care (POC) diagnostics, offering advantages such as cost-effectiveness, portability, and suitability for resource-constrained environments. By utilizing holographic principles and digital sensors, LIST enables high-resolution, lens-free imaging, making it ideal for rapid POC diagnostics in settings without traditional laboratory infrastructure. This review comprehensively explores recent advances and applications of LIST in various diagnostic fields, including pathogen detection, molecular diagnostics, environmental monitoring, telemedicine, and cancer diagnostics. We will discuss how integrating LIST with deep learning, microfluidics, and smartphone platforms further enhances diagnostic capabilities. In addition, challenges such as image noise and reconstruction artifacts will be addressed, and strategies will be developed to improve the functionality and scalability of LIST. Finally, future trends such as real-time monitoring, multiplex detection, and portable device integration are outlined to highlight the potential of LIST in expanding access to healthcare. This review aims to provide researchers with an insight into the transformative role of LIST in POC diagnostics and inspire further progress in this area.

1. Introduction

Point-of-care (POC) diagnostics has transformed healthcare by enabling rapid and accurate identification and monitoring of diseases directly at the patient's site.^[1-3] As the healthcare sector shifts to a consumer-centric model, the demand for accessible diagnostic services is increasing. In 2023, the global POC diagnostics market was valued at USD 60.52 billion and is expected to grow to USD 62.28 billion by 2024 and USD 82.78 billion by 2034.^[4] POC tests provide immediate results and enable faster medical decisions and prompt follow-up care.^[5,6] They are crucial for preventing, detecting, and treating chronic diseases, especially in remote areas.^[7] The advantages of POC diagnostics include rapid results that speed up decision-making and enable immediate treatment measures. Its portability allows it to be used in various settings, from urban hospitals to rural villages, and promotes equal access to healthcare.^[8] Many tests are user-friendly so that they can be performed effectively by healthcare professionals with minimal training.^[9] In addition, POC technologies are often more affordable, lowering cost barriers for marginalized populations and enabling greater accessibility. When used correctly and following established guidelines, POC testing can significantly increase the efficiency and effectiveness of medical treatments and ultimately improve the overall quality of patient care.

The synergistic integration of microfluidics, nanotechnology, and modern biosensor platforms has significantly advanced the development of POC diagnostics.^[10-12] This integration

has significantly improved the sensitivity, specificity, and multiplexing capability of POC devices, enabling the simultaneous detection of multiple biomarkers with exceptional accuracy.^[13-15] The development of innovative materials and sophisticated manufacturing techniques has led to the development of low-cost, highly sensitive, disposable diagnostic instruments that can be used in various environments, including those with limited resources. Recent breakthroughs in biosensor technology, including electrochemical, optical, and magnetic biosensors, have paved the way for novel POC diagnostic solutions characterized by high sensitivity and specificity — critical parameters essential for accurate disease detection and ongoing health monitoring.^[16,17] However, despite progress in this area, some challenges remain.

Among the innovative approaches that are changing POC diagnostics is lensless imaging (LI), which has proven to be a groundbreaking alternative to conventional diagnostic methods.^[18-22] LI and sensing technology (LIST) uses the principles of diffraction and holography to capture high-resolution images of objects without conventional lenses.^[23] In LIST, the diffraction pattern of an object projected onto a sensor is recorded, and then a high-resolution image is reconstructed with the help of computing algorithms.^[24] LIST offers several advantages over traditional lens-based imaging systems, including simplicity and cost-effectiveness, making it particularly useful in resource-constrained environments.^[25,26] The lensless system also provides a better depth of field (DOF) and a certain magnification factor but has a lower image sharpness.^[27] However, lens-based imaging struggles with problems such as the balance between spatial resolution and field of view (FOV), optical aberrations, and the inability to perform 3D measurements.^[28] LIST offers a hundred times larger FOV than conventional microscopy without compromising resolution, a combination quantified as the space-bandwidth product.^[27,29] The resolution of LIST is primarily determined by factors such as the pixel size of the image sensor and the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), while the FOV corresponds to the active area of the image sensor.^[29] For images, the space-bandwidth product is defined as the total image area divided by the square of the system resolution. To illustrate, a typical optical microscope with a 20x objective and a numerical aperture of 0.4 has a FOV of less than 1 mm² and a spatial resolution of 1.1 μm, resulting in a space-bandwidth of approximately 0.8 x 10⁶.^[30] In contrast, a lensless imaging (LFI) system using a CMOS image sensor with an active area of 40 mm² and a pixel size of 0.7 μm has a space-bandwidth of approximately 82 x 10⁶, around 100 times larger than the microscope. LIST is well suited for high-throughput biological sample analysis and lab-on-a-chip applications due to its large FOV, portability, and cost efficiency. Combining optical and fluidic technologies (optofluidics) has resulted in compact, affordable diagnostic devices that enable high-throughput screening and multiplex detection of analytes. Integrating these systems into smartphone platforms further improves accessibility and ease of use, enabling real-time data analysis and remote medical care.

LIST-based biosensors are used in various applications and have been studied by several authors.^[23,26,31-37] In this review, we will therefore focus on recent advances in LSI-based biosensors, highlighting in particular, their applications in on-site detection and point-of-care diagnostics. We will discuss the technological innovations underlying these advances, including deep learning algorithms, optofluidic integration, and smartphone-based platforms. In addition, we will explore the potential of these biosensors to address current challenges in POC diagnostics and their future prospects for improving global health outcomes.

2. Historical Overview

Figure 1 illustrates the timeline of the most critical developments in LIST, starting with the pioneering work of Dennis Gabor in the 1940s. In 1948, Gabor introduced an innovative

"microscopic principle" that eliminated the resolution limitations associated with electron lenses and paved the way for holography.^[38] He proposed a microscope that could circumvent the limitations of electron lenses and achieve resolutions beyond the conventional limit caused by spherical aberration. His proposal involved a two-step process: recording the interference pattern of an object illuminated by a coherent electron beam and then reconstructing the object using an optical system in which the resolution was limited only by the wavelength used and not by optical imperfections. This revolutionary idea laid the foundation for future advances in LIST. Gabor's method was to capture the Fresnel diffraction pattern of an object. Building on Gabor's work, researchers explored various methods for recording and reconstructing holograms. In 1961, Leith and Upatnieks demonstrated the first practical application of holography with lasers in which the hologram does not consist of a Fresnel diffraction pattern.^[39] They provided a communication framework for holography and showed an improved reconstruction of the signal-to-noise ratio compared to Gabor's original approach.

Figure 1. A timeline illustrating the evolution of lensless imaging and sensing technology.

In the 1960s and 1980s, holography experienced a significant advancement due to the contributions of researchers such as G. Liu and J. R. Fienup. Their work focused on solving the twin image problem and developing phase retrieval algorithms, which played a crucial role in improving the capabilities and applications of holography.^[40,41] However, a major limitation was the dependence on high-quality photographic plates and wet-chemical processing.^[42] With the introduction of digital image sensors towards the end of the 20th century, the landscape of holography began to change dramatically. A decisive moment came in 1994 when Ulf Schnars and Werner Jüptner at the University of Münster in Germany succeeded in recording holograms directly onto a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera.^[43] This innovative technique, known as "digital holography," revolutionized the field by enabling the numerical reconstruction of holographic images through computer algorithms.^[44] This advance simplified the holographic imaging process, improved the precision and versatility of holographic imaging, and opened up new avenues for research and application in various scientific and industrial fields.

In the 2000s, several groups adapted digital holography to microscopy applications using laser and light-emitting diode (LED) illumination sources.^[45-48] This period also saw the emergence of digital inline holography (DIH) (the optical axis of the light source is directly aligned with the detector and the sample under observation), which proved to be a

groundbreaking tool for biological research and achieved both lateral and depth resolution in the micrometer range.^[49,50] The integration of advanced fast reconstruction algorithms with DIH facilitated real-time imaging. It enabled researchers to visualize various objects, including microspheres and biological samples, with unprecedented clarity and precision. In this transformative decade, LIST developed into a distinct and innovative field, primarily due to the pioneering work of researchers such as Aydogan Ozcan and his team at the University of California, Los Angeles. They have shown that capturing high-resolution images of microscopic objects through lensless on-chip microscopy is possible, enabling high-resolution imaging and a large FOV. This advance has enabled the detection of individual nanoparticles and viruses, making the technology suitable for various biosensors and diagnostic applications.^[18,51,52] The most important innovation was using computational algorithms to reconstruct images from the interference patterns or shadows cast by objects. This breakthrough was a significant milestone as it demonstrated the potential of LI for biomedical applications, particularly in resource-constrained environments where conventional microscopes may be impractical due to their cost and complexity.

The integration of LIST with microfluidic devices further expanded the possibilities.^[53] This combination enables high-throughput analysis of biological samples and is ideal for POC diagnostics. Researchers such as Seo et al. have highlighted the potential of lensless on-chip microscopy for various biomedical applications.^[54,55] Using LEDs as illumination sources in lensless imaging has simplified the system and improved its cost efficiency.^[56,57] This made LIST more accessible to researchers and clinicians in resource-constrained environments.^[58-60]

In recent years, LIST has evolved, with researchers exploring new techniques and materials to improve its capabilities.^[61-66] The development of quantum dot image sensors has extended LIST's spectral range and improved its optical resolution and FOV.^[67,68] In addition, improvements such as shadow scanning lensless microscopy (SSLM) have achieved high spatial resolution by using a moving knife edge or wire to capture tomographic projection data, demonstrating that the method can work without wavelength limitations.^[69] In another study, plasmonic nanoparticles (NPs) were used for low-cost, high-throughput on-chip cytometry with a FOV of 24 mm².^[70,71] The plasmonic NPs, chosen for their high extinction coefficients and biocompatibility, enabled precise imaging and characterization. Analysis of the absorption spectra elucidated the effects of NP concentration. A deep phase neural network (DPNN) was used to achieve high spatial resolution and effectively restore sharp edges to improve image reconstruction.^[72] In addition, a parallel dual-branch fusion model has been proposed that combines the two primary reconstruction strategies: the model-based approach and the purely data-driven deep neural network (DNN).^[73] Recently, LI has been used for 3D imaging.^[74-76] Wu et al. captured detailed 3D images with high resolution, covering a large area and depth.^[77] It uses a range of light wavelengths to reconstruct the sample's 3D structure, achieving a lateral resolution of 775 nm and an axial resolution of 5.43 μm .

LIST is a rapidly developing field with a promising future. Its simplicity, portability, and cost-effectiveness make it a valuable tool for a wide range of applications, from biomedical diagnostics and cell characterization to industrial metrology and environmental monitoring.^[78-89] As research continues, we can expect even more exciting advances in this lensless approach to imaging.

2. Technical Aspects of Lensless Imaging and Sensing Technology

2.1. Principle and Working Mechanism

As already mentioned, LIST is based on the principle of inline holography. In inline holography, the reference and object waves travel along the same optical path. This happens when a wave hits an object, causing part of the wave to scatter and form the object wave, while the remaining unscattered part becomes the reference wave. In digital holography, the image is captured in real space, but the hologram is captured with an electronic camera, e.g., a CCD or a complementary metal–oxide–semiconductor (CMOS) camera, and transferred to a computer in digital form. This enables numerical processing of the shadows (digital holograms), which offers unique features and capabilities, such as the ability to create holograms of fictitious objects that are unlikely or impossible in real space and the ability to overlay multiple holograms illuminated with different lenses.^[90]

Figure 2. This figure illustrates two configurations for lensless imaging. (A) Configuration using a coherent light source. (B) Configuration using an incoherent light source.

Figure 2 shows the conventional configuration of lensless imaging, where the light source is at a distance of z_1 above the sample, and the sample is at a distance of z_2 above the surface of the image sensor. A small aperture and a coherent light source (e.g., a laser) are used, where $z_1 < z_2$. For incoherent or partially coherent lensless on-chip imaging platforms, a relatively larger aperture and an incoherent or partially coherent light source are used, where $z_2 \ll z_1$. z_2 is usually < 1 mm. The basic principle of LIST is the interference that occurs when coherent light passes through or interacts with an object. This interference pattern contains valuable information about the shape and features of the object and can be captured by a sensor placed in the path of the scattered light. Advanced computational algorithms are then used to analyze the intensity variations and patterns within the interference pattern to reconstruct a high-resolution image of the object. The simulations and reconstructions of digital holography are based on fast Fourier transform (FFT). While most methods usually use a single FFT, using two FFTs, as in the angular spectrum method for plane waves, often leads to optimal reconstructions. The advantages of this approach are mainly due to two factors: the balanced sampling of the object and its hologram and the reduced dependence on parameters such as distance, pixel count, wavelength, and object and detector size. By using two FFTs, it is possible to adjust the number of pixels without compromising the accuracy of the reconstruction. The numerical procedures for reconstructing holograms recorded with plane and spherical waves are identical if the reconstruction algorithms include similar steps, such as the inverse Fourier transform and multiplication by the spherical phase factor followed by a Fourier transform.^[91]

There are two main types of lensless imaging: non-contact and contact. Non-contact imaging captures either diffraction patterns for 3D reconstruction (diffraction shadow imaging) or emitted light for contrast enhancement and analysis (luminescence imaging). In contrast, contact imaging captures shadows for 2D imaging (shadow-based imaging) or emitted light for analysis (luminescence-based imaging). Each category has its own advantages and limitations, and the choice of imaging technique ultimately depends on the application and the requirements of the individual case.^[28] Luminescence imaging, in which the photons emitted by the sample are detected in the form of fluorescence, chemiluminescence, electrochemiluminescence, and bioluminescence, is not included in this review. In addition, we also exclude contact-based imaging, where the geometric shadow of the object has a clearly defined edge and minimal diffraction.

3.2. Image Formation and Reconstruction

3.2.1. Diffraction Pattern Formation

In LIST, imaging is achieved by interacting light with the sample, resulting in diffraction patterns. When a coherent light source illuminates a sample, the light waves interact with the microscopic structures within the sample, scattering the light in different directions and creating a complex interference pattern known as a hologram.^[92] This hologram is a three-dimensional representation of the object's information encoded in the light field.

LIST captures the hologram directly with an image sensor without conventional lenses. Although the resulting image appears as a shadow, it contains the necessary information to reconstruct the object's three-dimensional structure. The principles of this process are illustrated in Figure 3, which shows the lensless imaging system. Several factors, including the coherence of the light source, the distance between the object and the image sensor, and the sensor's pixel size, influence the quality of the captured hologram.^[93] The diffraction data is then reconstructed using computational algorithms, often based on Fourier transforms, to obtain the final image.^[94,95] The resolution and accuracy of the final image depend on the quality of the diffraction pattern, which is influenced by the coherence of the light source, the wavelength of the light, and the properties of the sample.

Figure 3. Principle of the lensless imaging system. The diagram illustrates the interaction of incident light with an object, which leads to the formation of bright rings and shadow areas on the sensor. Adapted with permission.^[80] Copyright 2020 John Wiley and Sons.

3.2.1. Diffraction Pattern Formation

The optical field reaching the sample plane can be considered coherent when using a monochromatic light source with a small aperture. The inline hologram recorded on the image sensor is generated by superimposing the light scattered from the sample with an undisturbed reference wave propagating through the transparent substrate. This digitally recorded intensity image can be expressed as follows:^[29]

$$I(x, y, z_i) = |E(x, y, z_i)|^2 \quad (1)$$

$$I(x, y, z_i) = |E_r(x, y, z_i) + E_o(x, y, z_i)|^2 \quad (2)$$

$$I(x, y, z_i) = |E_r(x, y, z_i)|^2 + |E_o(x, y, z_i)|^2 + E_r^*(x, y, z_i)E_o(x, y, z_i) + E_r(x, y, z_i)E_o^*(x, y, z_i) \quad (3)$$

In the sample plane where the light interacts, the intensity can be described as the sum of the reference wave $E_r(x, y, z_i)$ and the object wave $E_o(x, y, z_s)$.

$$I(x, y, z_i) = A_r^2 + A_r e^{-ikz_2} T_{z_2} \{E_o(x, y, z_s)\} + A_r e^{-ikz_2} [T_{z_2} \{E_o(x, y, z_s)\}]^* + |T_{z_2} \{E_o(x, y, z_s)\}|^2 \quad (4)$$

Where * is the conjugate complex of the operator, $k = \frac{2\pi n}{\lambda}$ is the wave number, A_r is a constant, $A_r e^{ikz_2}$ is the reference plane wave, and T_z is the forward propagation operator, where $E(x, y, z) \equiv T_z \{E(x, y, 0)\}$.

The angular spectrum method can be used to reconstruct the amplitude and phase of the object from the recorded hologram. This approach includes the following steps:^[23]

1. Calculating the Fourier transform of the captured hologram: This involves converting the hologram from the spatial domain to the frequency domain.
2. Multiplying the Fourier-transformed hologram by the corresponding transfer function of free space: This transfer function considers the propagation of the wave field from the hologram plane to the object plane.
3. Performing an inverse Fourier transform of the modified spectrum: This transforms the wavefield back into the spatial domain and reconstructs the amplitude and phase properties of the original object.

Mathematically, the transfer functions are in the form of spatial frequencies ξ and η are defined as:

$$E(x, y, z) = \mathcal{F}^{-1}[\mathcal{F}\{E(x, y, 0)\}H(\xi, \eta, z)] \quad (5)$$

where,

$$(\xi, \eta, z) = \begin{cases} 0, \text{ for } \xi^2 + \eta^2 \geq \frac{n^2}{\lambda^2} \\ e^{2\pi i z \sqrt{\frac{n^2}{\lambda^2} - \xi^2 - \eta^2}}, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The process can be simplified when reconstructing holograms if the object wave is much weaker than the reference wave. Specific terms in the equation, such as the one in equation (4), $|T_{z_2} \{E_o(x, y, z_s)\}|^2$ can be neglected under this assumption unless the object is very dense or thick^{22,28}.

To reconstruct the object image from the recorded hologram with light waves, a "backpropagation" of the intensity image $I(x, y, z_i)$ must be performed.^[96] In backpropagation, a wave pattern is reversed to localize its source. This method results in a "reconstructed field" that contains the desired object image and a "twin image," an unwanted duplicate that makes reconstruction more difficult.

The backpropagation process occurs at a distance z_2 from the sample plane in which the object is positioned. FFTs (Fast Fourier Transforms) help simplify complex wave patterns for efficient processing. In an off-axis setup, the twin image is spatially separated from the object and can be easily removed. However, in an inline setup, the twin image overlaps with the object, making separation difficult. Various techniques are available to remove unwanted artifacts, such as the twin image, and improve the clarity of the final image.

4. Recent Advances in Lensless Imaging-Based Biosensors

4.1. Pathogen Detection

LIST has proven to be a powerful tool for detecting pathogens, providing rapid, accurate, and cost-effective solutions for various applications. This section reviews LIST's application for detecting bacterial, viral, and other pathogenic organisms, emphasizing its usefulness in clinical and environmental settings.^[97]

A. Detection of Pathogenic Bacteria

LIST is particularly effective in detecting pathogenic bacteria in biological samples such as blood, urine, and sputum.^[97-100] McKay et al. investigated the potential of LIST for bedside diagnosis of urinary tract infections (UTI).^[98] The study highlighted LIST's ability to accurately identify key urine components such as blood cells and crystals while detecting urinary problems such as hematuria and pyuria. LIST effectively estimated *E. coli* concentrations and strongly correlated with conventional hematology measurements ($R^2 > 99\%$). The study also showed that LIST can differentiate between UTI-positive and UTI-negative samples. However, further research is needed to improve the sensitivity and to solve problems such as crosstalk between different particle concentrations in urine samples. In addition, Poher et al. presented a method to enhance bacterial detection by using a thin wetting film.^[101] Combined with inline holographic reconstruction, this approach achieved up to 92% accuracy for micrometer-sized objects at various concentrations, successfully detecting concentrations ranging from single bacteria to densely packed objects with a range of up to 1000 bacteria per microliter.

B. Bacterial Growth Tracking

In another study, LIST was combined with live cells and a two-stage deep learning architecture to track the growth kinetics of bacterial microcolonies over time (see Figure 4A).^[102] Paquin et al. used the kinetic growth patterns of microcolonies between 10 μm and 500 μm in size in combination with a two-stage deep learning architecture. In their study, a lensless live-cell imaging system and a thin-layer agar medium with 20 μl brain heart infusion broth were used to capture the growth of bacterial colonies in time-lapse. The data set included seven different bacterial strains: *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecium*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* R6, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and *Lactococcus lactis*. Data collection was culture-dependent, with the number of bacterial colonies observed varying according to species and experimental conditions. For example, the number

of colonies ranged from 50 per test for *E. faecium* to 300 per sample for *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*. This study used deep learning architectures such as convolutional networks and recurrent neural networks to extract spatio-temporal patterns from unreconstructed lensless microscopy time-lapse images. This innovative approach enabled the rapid detection and classification of bacterial colonies. To compensate for the imbalance of classes due to the different numbers of colonies in the various species, the networks were trained to give more importance to classes with fewer colonies. This method enabled label-free phenotypic characterization, which made it possible to distinguish between pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The detection network achieved a success rate of 96%, while the classification network achieved a precision of 93.1 % with an overall sensitivity of almost 94% (see Figure 4B).

Figure 4. (A) Growth kinetics of various bacterial microcolonies, including *Lactococcus lactis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Enterococcus faecium*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes*, monitored over a 12 h incubation period with 30 min intervals. Each image represents a 64×64 pixel image ($107 \times 107 \mu\text{m}$), allowing label-free phenotypic characterization and differentiation of pathogenic bacteria. (B) Performance metrics of the two-stage deep learning architecture in bacterial classification. (a) Precision and (b) sensitivity are tracked over the 12 h incubation period. The green shaded area shows the variation between maximum and minimum sensitivity at each time point across all species. (C) Schematic representation of reflection-based dark-field microscopy (RDFM) setup with oblique illumination. (a) Front view with multi-angle illumination from 0° to 90°. (b) Side view of the illumination setup. (c) An illustration of a bead on the CMOS sensor shows how shadow length is used to calculate object height. (d) Detailed view of light interaction with CMOS sensor components at large illumination angles. (D) Image results of a fixed *Staphylococcus epidermidis* under different illumination angles. (a) Visibility enhancement of the

bacteria, whose size is comparable to that of the CMOS sensor pixels, is pronounced at angles between 70° and 90°. (b) The diagram shows a twofold reduction in background intensity at larger angles due to Fresnel reflection, resulting in improved contrast. Scale bar: 5 μm . (A), (B) Adapted under terms of the CC-BY license from ^[102]. Copyright 2022 PLOS. (C), (D) Adapted under terms of the CC-BY license from ^[103]. Copyright 2020 Optical Society of America.

C. Advanced Imaging Platforms

An LI platform with oblique illumination for reflection-based dark-field microscopy (RDFM) at the sensor and 3D object measurements was also developed (see Figure 4C).^[103] This platform has two imaging modalities: shadow imaging to estimate 3D object dimensions and dark-field imaging to enhance contrast, which is particularly suitable for analyzing clusters of bacteria and algae. The system achieves a spatial resolution limited by the sensor's pixel size, approximately 1.4 μm , over the entire sensor area of 3.6 mm \times 2.73 mm. At more than 85° illumination angles, the RDFM system operates in dark field mode. This mode is characterized by a significant reduction in background intensity and contrast reversal, similar to traditional dark-field microscopy. These features significantly improve the visibility of morphological details in bacteria and unicellular algal clusters. Figure 4D shows the imaging results of *S. epidermidis* under different illumination angles.

D. Viral Detection Capabilities

LIST effectively detects viruses, including those responsible for malaria and COVID-19. Bishara et al. used a pixel super-resolution algorithm to improve image resolution for field use and successfully imaged *Plasmodium falciparum* in blood smears, enabling rapid malaria diagnosis.^[104]

LIST has also been successfully used to detect viruses, significantly reducing the time required for conventional plaque assays. Liu et al. demonstrated this by detecting viruses such as vesicular stomatitis virus (VSV), herpes simplex virus (HSV-1), and encephalomyocarditis virus (EMCV).^[97] Their method drastically shortened incubation times, detecting HSV-1 within approximately 48 h and EMCV in only 20 h, compared to the long times required for conventional tests. VSV replication was observed as early as five hour after incubation. Figure 5A illustrates the workflow of the label-free viral plaque assay and its comparison with the standard PFU assay. The steps include sample preparation for the plaque assay, image processing, and the application of a neural network-based PFU classifier, resulting in efficient detection with an accuracy of over 90% within 20 h — significantly faster than the conventional 48-h incubation, with VSV replication, observed as early as 5 h after incubation. The system demonstrated a high detection rate for HSV-1, achieving an accuracy of 90.4% after only 72 h, a significant time saving of 48 h compared to the conventional 120-h test duration. In addition, a detection rate of 90.8% was achieved for EMCV after 52 h, a time saving of approximately 20 h compared to conventional methods. This performance is illustrated in Figure 5B, which shows the efficacy of the stain-free plaque assay for samples with low virus concentration, including a comparison of results after different incubation times.

Figure 5. (A) Schematic overview of the label-free viral plaque assay workflow and its comparison with the standard plaque-forming unit (PFU) assay. (a) Overview of sample preparation for the plaque assay, where the conventional plaque assay is performed for comparison purposes only and is not required to operate the PFU detection device. (b) Image processing steps in the reconstruction and registration of successive whole-well holograms. (c) Example of network processing within a localized FOV. (d) Illustration of a PFU probability map for a single well. (e) Conversion of the PFU probability map into detection results after applying a threshold of 0.5. (f) Example of PFU detection results for an entire six-well plate after 5 h of incubation. (B) Performance of the stain-free viral plaque assay for samples with low virus concentrations. (a) Comparison between the stain-free viral plaque assay after 17 h of incubation and the conventional plaque assay after 48 h of incubation and staining. (b) Over time, the average detection rate of plaque-forming units (PFU) with the label-free viral plaque assay was 90.4% for HSV-1 after 72 h and 90.8% for EMCV after 52 h. The error bars represent the standard deviation of five test plates. Adapted under terms of the CC-BY license from ^[97] Copyright 2023 Springer Nature.

One of the main advantages of this method is its ability to deal with high virus concentrations. In such cases, plaque-forming units (PFUs) accumulate rapidly, making manual

counting impractical. However, the LFI-based system provides quantitative readings and creates a PFU probability map that enables precise measurements of virus-infected areas over time. In addition, the system proves to be robust against typical artifacts that occur during sample preparation, such as temperature fluctuations or changes in the optical field in the incubator. The deep learning algorithms integrated into the system efficiently distinguish between actual PFUs and these artifacts and ensure high accuracy despite environmental fluctuations.

Ray et al. proposed a new computational sensing technique for detecting HSV that combines the immune specificity of virus-specific antibodies with the physical size of virus particles to achieve high sensitivity.^[105] Their approach involves two crucial steps: virus capture using antibodies and subsequent imaging and sizing of the particles to confirm detection (Figure 6A). To capture the virus, the biotin-streptavidin conjugation system is used, which ensures specific interactions, while the non-specific binding is minimized by using m-PEG1000 coatings. To amplify the optical signals and improve the signal-to-noise ratio, polyethylene glycol-based nano-lenses are built around each virus particle, which can be used to reconstruct holographic images of the viruses. These holograms are then used to automatically quantify the virus particle size over a large FOV (approximately 30 mm²). The study also estimates the system's limit of detection (LOD), which is approximately four HSV-1 particles per mm² FOV, translating to approximately 120 counts for the entire area of the CMOS imager chip at a 100 percent recovery rate. Counting viral particles in a sample is critical for determining disease severity and monitoring the effectiveness of antiviral therapy. The computational sensing method developed in this study can be extended to other virus types and provides a versatile tool for virus detection.

Figure 6. (A) Overview of sensor technology for detecting herpes simplex virus (HSV): (a) Virus capture with a biotin-streptavidin system on m-PEG1000-coated glass to reduce non-specific binding. (b) Histogram of HSV-1 particle size distribution from imaging data. (c) Diagram correlating the initial virus particle number with the observed number per mm², showing a detection limit at ~ 4 HSV-1 particles/mm² ($\mu + 3\sigma$). (B) Schematic of lensless imaging biosensor for SARS-CoV-2 detection by particle agglutination: (a) ACE2-functionalized microbeads prepared by incubation of polystyrene beads with biotinylated ACE2 and streptavidin. (b) Bead agglutination after exposure to SARS-CoV-2 pseudovirus. (c) The assay was loaded into the imaging chip via a micropipette. (c) Quantification of microbead agglutination with SARS-CoV-2 pseudovirus. (a) Bound rate versus virus concentration, with negative control VSV-G negative control showing no response (10.66% standard deviation). (b) Convolutional neural network-based quantification with improved standard deviation (3.89 %). The blue curve ($R^2 = 0.974$) shows a detection limit of 1,270 viral copies/mL. The red dashed lines indicate the LOD cutoffs, and the black dots represent triplicate samples, with the error bars indicating the standard error. (A) Adapted with permission from [105]. Copyright 2023 Springer Nature. (B), (C) Reprinted with permission from [106]. Copyright 2001 Royal Society of Chemistry.

The study mentions several challenges associated with the virus detection method. A significant problem is the possible decay of viruses during routine handling, e.g., centrifugation or pipetting, which can lead to size errors and undetected virus particles. In addition, the presence of virus clusters or closely spaced viruses can affect the topology of the nanosensors, further complicating accurate sizing.

E. COVID-19 Detection Innovations

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the urgent need for rapid diagnostic tools accelerated the development of LIST-based biosensors for SARS-CoV-2 detection.^[106,107] Potter et al. introduced an innovative approach combining LIST with deep learning algorithms to develop a wearable biosensor for COVID-19 detection.^[106] In the study, a particle agglutination test (see Figure 6B) describes the procedure for producing ACE2-functionalized microbeads and their interaction with the SARS-CoV-2 pseudovirus. A pseudovirus model, VSV-G, was used for the study, filtered and diluted in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium at various concentrations. The resulting samples, consisting of functionalized microbeads and pseudoviruses, were incubated and analyzed with an imaging chip, providing a novel method for rapid virus detection.

The system effectively detected SARS-CoV-2 pseudovirus concentrations as low as 1270 copies per mL, with a test duration of only three hours and a requirement of only 40 μ L virus sample per test (Figure 6C). This LOD is comparable to the sensitivity of RT-PCR tests and significantly exceeds the sensitivity of lateral flow assays (LFAs) for SARS-CoV-2. The deep learning algorithm used in the biosensor achieved high accuracy in distinguishing microsphere agglutinations from other particles and boasted an accuracy of 88.58% in real-world applications. This progress underlines the potential of LIST-based biosensors for pandemic response and virus detection.

4.2. Molecular Diagnostics

LIST has shown great promise in analyzing molecular patterns in biological samples, especially by integrating advanced techniques such as deep learning, holography, and opto-magnetic systems.

A. Amplification-Free Nucleic Acid Detection

A significant advance in LIST is the development of a portable, deep learning-based platform for the amplification-free detection of nucleic acids.^[108] This platform effectively distinguishes between viable and non-viable *Salmonella typhimurium* with high sensitivity (72 CFU/mL) and without pre-amplification. The system utilizes phage-mediated DNA extraction, proving its efficiency in nucleic acid detection.

At its core, the platform uses an advanced YOLOv7 deep learning algorithm specifically trained to recognize small objects ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) in high-resolution holographic images. The workflow starts with generating a hologram using an LIST-based microscope that captures the phase variations in the sample. Pre-processing steps such as background subtraction, amplitude sensitive pixel reconstruction (ASP) and bilateral filtering improve the image quality. The processed image, represented by pixel intensity values, is fed into the YOLOv7 convolutional neural network (CNN), which employs layers such as efficient layer aggregation networks (ELAN), concatenation, upsampling, and spatial pyramid pooling (SPP) to detect small

particles. The output creates bounding boxes around the detected particles, allowing accurate object counting without target amplification.

This versatile platform connects to a laptop for real-time analysis and can detect various targets, including biomarkers, making it suitable for diagnostic applications. As shown in Figure 7A, this setup improves the algorithm's ability to identify and classify small particles, increasing detection sensitivity accurately. Unlike traditional digital assays that require pre-amplification, this platform simplifies the detection process, reduces the need for expensive equipment, and expands its applicability to various fields. In addition, non-nucleic acid targets, such as procalcitonin and chloramphenicol, can also be detected in multiple actual samples.

B. Large-Area Binding Sensor for Biomolecular Analysis

Xiong et al. presented the QLAB (quantitative large-area binding) sensor, which combines LIST with a bead-based agglutination test.^[109] In this sensor, beads functionalized with capture agents bind to the target analytes in solution, resulting in agglutination (see Figure 7B). The QLAB sensor uses a high-speed lensless holographic microscope to image and resolve beads in solution, enabling simultaneous imaging of up to 10,000 beads in Brownian motion. This capability improves the signal-to-noise ratio over a large field of view. Binding is quantified by measuring the distribution of bead cluster sizes, which correlates directly with the concentration of the target analyte. The sensor achieves a LOD of 27 ng/mL for NeutrAvidin protein molecules and 3 ng/mL for mouse interferon-gamma (IFN-g) molecules, demonstrating its effectiveness in detecting clinically relevant levels of protein biomarkers.

Figure 7. (A) Schematic representation of the CNN-based image processing workflow for amplification-free nucleic acid detection. The left section shows the hologram acquisition with the portable light holographic microscope (PLH), followed by background subtraction, ASP reconstruction, and bilateral filtering to enhance the signals. The YOLOv7 deep learning network processes the reconstructed image optimized for small object detection ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$). The final output includes bounding box predictions, shown on the right, with 13 detected particles. (B) Schematic representation of the quantitative large-area binding (QLAB) sensor and its operating principle. (a) Beads functionalized with capture agents incubate with analytes. (b) Introduction of the sample into a microfluidic chamber (MC). (c) MC on a complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor sensor. (d) Schematic representation of the binding between biotin-coated beads and NeutrAvidin molecules. (e) Illustration of the binding between anti-mouse IFN- γ -coated beads and mouse IFN- γ molecules. (f) Sensor response for mouse IFN- γ , with BSA as negative control. (g) Illustrations of monomer and bead clusters. (A) Reprinted with permission from ^[108]. Copyright 2024 Elsevier. (B) Reprinted with permission from ^[109]. Copyright 2021 American Chemical Society.

C. Opto-Magnetic System for DNA Detection

Another innovative application is a novel opto-magnetic system that uses LIST for the optical readout of surface-hybridized DNA fragments.^[110] In this system, the DNA is labeled by magnetic particles attracted to the detection surface and completes the labeling process in less than a minute, as shown in Figure 8A. The efficiency of this approach is enhanced by an

optimized surface functionalization protocol coupled with a magnetic manipulation that effectively removes non-specifically bound particles from the detection surface. This ensures that only explicitly bound particles are imaged, enabling the detection of DNA concentrations as low as 10 pM with single particle sensitivity.

A key feature of this system is the ability to integrate sample preparation and analyte detection in a single test. The manipulation of the magnetic particles not only accelerates the labeling of the hybridized DNA fragments, but also helps to remove unbound particles, which increases the sensitivity and specificity of the test. This is further illustrated in Figure 8B, which shows the imaging and reconstruction process. The interference pattern recorded by the CMOS imager shows clear features when the reconstruction distance is correct, while deviations result in blurred images, similar to blurred photographs.

D. Ultraviolet Wavelength Imaging

LIST at ultraviolet (UV) wavelengths was investigated for imaging nanoparticles and biomolecular aggregates (Figure 8C).^[111] Daloglu et al. demonstrated significantly higher contrast in amplitude reconstructions of superoxide dismutase 1 (SOD1) protein aggregates illuminated at 266 nm compared to longer wavelengths such as blue, green, and red. UV light in this imaging platform is crucial as it increases the scattering cross-section of nanoparticles, thereby improving imaging contrast and resolution. UV wavelengths, particularly at 266 nm, are strongly absorbed by biomolecules such as proteins and nucleic acids, allowing high-contrast imaging of these entities. This property is particularly advantageous for imaging aggregates of biomolecules such as Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase, which are associated with neurodegenerative diseases such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). Figure 8C(a) shows that the amplitude reconstructions of SOD1 aggregates exhibit significantly higher contrast at 266 nm illumination, while (b), (e), and (f) show weaker contrast at blue, green, and red wavelengths, respectively. The higher contrast at 266 nm is due to the increased forward scattering and absorption of UV light by biomolecules, which are not as pronounced at longer wavelengths. The research highlights the potential of UV light to simplify the illumination front end of imaging platforms, particularly with advances in LED technology in the mid to far UV range.

Figure 8. (A) Overview of the manipulation steps for magnetic particles in DNA tests. (a) Magnetic attraction enables rapid labeling of DNA with magnetic particles. (b) Repulsion of the magnets over the sensing substrate removes unbound particles. (c) Unbound magnetic particles are removed from the field of view with a toroidal-shaped magnet during lensless imaging. (B) Imaging and reconstruction process in the opto-magnetic system. (a) The interference pattern of a reference structure is recorded with the CMOS sensor. (b) If the reconstruction distance is correct, the number '4' and individual magnetic particles can be recognized. (c) An incorrect reconstruction distance leads to a blurred image reminiscent of a blurred photo. (C) Imaging of SOD1 protein aggregates with LIST at different wavelengths. (a) Amplitude reconstructions of SOD1 aggregates at 266 nm show significantly higher contrast. (b), (e) and (f) Amplitude reconstructions at blue, green, and red wavelengths show weaker contrast. (c) and (d) Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of SOD1 aggregates. (g) The absorption spectrum of SOD1 aggregates shows higher absorption at 266 nm light compared to the visible region. (A), (B) Adapted with permission from ^[110]. Copyright 2001 Royal Society of Chemistry. (C) Reprinted with permission from ^[111]. Copyright 2018 SPIE.

E. Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) Integration

Sly et al. explored the innovative use of lensless surface second harmonic generation imaging (SSHGI) to visualize SHG active molecules, specifically (S)-(+)-1,1'-Bi-2-naphthol (SBN), incorporated into a lipid bilayer. This research leverages the coherent plane-wave nature of SHG.^[112] The study highlights that lensless SSHGI is sensitive to wave-front curvature, with diffraction effects observed at a curvature degree as low as 20°. It also notes a discrepancy

between experimentally determined and theoretical confocal distances attributed to non-ideal planar wave-fronts of the incoming beams. Furthermore, the research provides theoretical insights into the coherence and planar waveform of surface SHG, which minimizes diffraction and enables effective lensless imaging. This approach stands in contrast to lensless fluorescence imaging, which typically requires an objective lens to generate spherical wavefronts. By offering a more straightforward and more efficient method for SHG surface imaging, this study paves the way for advancements in molecular diagnostics and serves as a valuable tool for researchers and clinicians in the field.

4.3. Environmental Monitoring

LIST has proven to be a versatile and cost-effective tool for environmental monitoring, with applications ranging from protein sensing to air quality assessment. Its adaptability makes it valuable in both environmental and biological contexts.^[113-115]

A. Ultrafine Air Pollution Monitoring

A significant advance in the field of LIST is its use in monitoring ultrafine air pollution.^[116,117] A novel air quality monitoring device, the lensless particle air quality detector (LPAQD), has been developed to detect and quantify particles in the range of 0.1 to 10 μm , overcoming the limitations of current commercial air quality monitoring systems. These conventional systems often lack an extensive dynamic range, especially for ultrafine particles, and are usually expensive and stationary. The LPAQD can detect particles as small as 100 nm and track measurements in real time, as shown in Figure 9A. One of the most important innovations in this system is using a vapor-condensed film that improves the detection of subpixels and sub-diffraction-limit by increasing their scattering cross-section. This film forms a meniscus around the particles and creates a nano lens effect that enhances light scattering, making smaller particles more visible in lensless holographic images. This amplification increases the SNR and facilitates these particles' detection, sizing, and counting. A key finding of the study is that a 5-min deposition of the vapor-condensed film was optimal for nano lens formation, which improved detection performance. The LPAQD correlated with commercial devices in detecting changes in PM 2.5 concentration, although the LPAQD measures particle number while commercial devices measure total mass. The detection efficiency (η) of the LPAQD was calculated to be 1.91×10^{-4} , which allows the conversion of particle count data to PM concentrations. Validation against the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency performance test protocols yielded a coefficient of determination (R^2) of ≥ 0.70 for linearity, as shown in Figure 10B. The 10-megapixel sensor can detect up to 10^5 particles, with saturation expected within 10 h at a $100 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ concentration.

Other significant advances include integrating vacuum pumps and impaction nozzles, which enable the collection of airborne particles on optically transparent substrates. In addition, machine learning algorithms process holographic images and diffraction patterns to accurately determine particle size, density, and type. This combination of advanced features makes the LPAQD a cost-effective, portable, and sensitive solution for real-time air quality monitoring, particularly for detecting ultrafine particles, which are critical to environmental health and public safety.^[118]

Figure 9. (A) Nanosensing effects for 1 μm and 100 nm spherical nanoparticles using the lensless particle air quality detector (LPAQD). (a) Reconstructed hologram from the diffraction pattern of aerosolized 1 μm particles deposited on PEG film. (b) Fluorescence microscopy confirms the location of the 1 μm particles. (c) Reconstructed hologram from the diffraction pattern of aerosolized 100 nm nanoparticles on PEG film, with insets showing SEM images confirming the location of the particles (scale bars: 100 nm). (B) The correlation between new particles counted hourly in the LPAQD, and hourly PM_{2.5} concentrations reported by the district shows the performance of the LPAQD compared to commercial devices. Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY license from [116]. Copyright © 2023 American Chemical Society.

B. Bioluminescence Whole-Cell Sensor Arrays

Beyond air quality, LIST has been integrated into bioluminescence whole-cell sensor arrays, such as the LumiChip platform.^[119] This technology recognizes class-specific toxins based on their biological activity using genetically modified *E. coli* strains. These bacteria are designed to respond to environmental toxins by combining stress-responsive gene promoters with bioluminescent genes. The LumiChip platform utilizes a linear CCD for highly efficient light collection, enabling rapid detection of contaminants within 15 to 45 min. This application demonstrates the versatility of LIST in environmental monitoring by utilizing biological systems for the sensitive and rapid detection of contaminants.

C. Marine Environment Monitoring

The application of LIST has been extended to the marine environment with a portable platform for monitoring the toxicity of seawater.^[84] The platform assesses the ecotoxicity of hazardous and noxious substances (HNS) in these environments. An important study investigated the relationship between growth rate and morphological changes in the marine alga *Dunaliella tertiolecta* when exposed to different HNS. In the study, the LIST was used to monitor and analyze morphological changes in *D. tertiolecta* cells at different HNS concentrations. Figure 10A shows visual representations of live (healthy), live (cyst), and dead cells using light and shadow microscopy. The images illustrate the distinct morphological changes associated with the different cell states. These morphological changes were quantified by analyzing shadow parameters, and the different cell states were identified: live cells were elliptical, cystic cells appeared swollen, and dead cells were deflated. Figure 10B shows a scatter plot illustrating the relationship between the circular ratio and the central maximum value (CMV) values for the three cell types, distinguishing between the cell stages based on their morphological characteristics. Figure 10D compares the circular ratio of control and exposed cells to various chemicals. Under toxic conditions, *D. tertiolecta* cells showed a clear transition from an elliptical shape to a more circular morphology, eventually leading to cell wall disintegration and death.

Figure 10C shows correlation plots between growth rate, healthy ratio, and chemical concentration for four different chemicals: ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, acetone, and sulfuric acid, showing the effects of each chemical on cell growth and morphology. After exposure to HNS, the correlation coefficients for the different substances ranged from 0.57 to 0.95, with an average value of 0.84, indicating a strong correlation. Interestingly, the morphological changes proved to be more sensitive indicators of toxicity than the growth rate, especially after longer exposure times of 3 and 6 h. The platform proved effective for 20 of the 30 HNS tested, and the method could provide results in as little as 5 min. The research results indicate that morphological analysis with LIST delivers a faster and more sensitive toxicity assessment than conventional growth rate methods. This demonstrates that LIST has the potential to be utilized for on-site toxicity monitoring in marine environments, offering timely and dependable data that is crucial for environmental protection and the well-being of marine ecosystems.

Figure 10. (A) Optical and shadow images of live (healthy), live (cyst), and dead cells. (B) Scatter plot showing the distribution of circulation ratio and CMV values for different cell types. (C) Correlation plots between growth rate (growth inhibition assay), healthy ratio (morphology change assay), and chemical concentration for ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, acetone, and sulfuric acid. (D) Bar graph comparing the circular ratio of control cells and cells exposed to 50 HNS. Adapted with permission from [84]. Copyright 2023 Elsevier.

4.4. Telemedicine Device for Cell Analysis

LIST has established itself as an effective and versatile tool for cell analysis and offers a compact, high-throughput alternative to conventional microscopy.^[108,120,121] By eliminating bulky optical components and using digital data processing, LIST offers a lightweight and portable solution that is particularly beneficial in resource-constrained environments.^[34]

A. Integration with Smartphone Applications

LIST can be integrated into smartphone applications for telemedicine and enables image processing and remote diagnosis in real time. Roy et al. have developed a system capable of wirelessly transmitting lensless images to smartphones, where an Android application processes the images using a moving window thresholding technique to account for non-uniform background intensities (Figure 11A).^[122] The LIST system is particularly advantageous in resource-constrained or remote environments, as it can analyze the processed images on-site and transmit the results remotely for further evaluation by experts. Validations have strongly correlated with conventional light microscopy (coefficient of 0.91), underlining its clinical reliability.

LIST has proven its suitability for various diagnostic procedures, e.g., to determine the complete blood count (CBC). A notable study compared LIST results to a standard hematology analyzer for red and white blood cell counts, with strong correlation indices of 0.878 for red blood cells and 0.927 for white blood cells. The linearity comparison resulted in an R^2 value of 0.99 for erythrocytes and 0.92 for leukocytes, underlining its accuracy. LIST also successfully differentiated the subtypes of leukocytes and achieved correlation coefficients of over 0.90 for neutrophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes (Figure 11B). The mean error rates were 10.26 % for neutrophils, 9.74 % for lymphocytes, and 4.09 % for monocytes.

Figure 11. (A) Schematic illustration of the lensless shadow imaging system for smartphone-based imaging and remote diagnosis. (B) Comparison of red blood cell (RBC) and white blood cell (WBC) counts between the LIST system and the standard hematology analyzer (LH 750). (a) Red blood cell concentrations in 21 samples. (b) Linearity comparison of RBC detection between LIST and LH 750. (c) Calibrated RBC results from regression analysis. (d) WBC concentrations in 21 samples. (e) Comparison of linearity of WBC detection. (f) Calibrated WBC results from the regression analysis. Reprinted with permission from ^[123]. Copyright 2014 Elsevier.

A significant advantage of the LIST system is its affordability. Because it consists of inexpensive optoelectronic components such as a conjugated micro-pinhole LED (\$3) and a lensless CMOS image sensor (\$14), the cost of the device is negligible compared to conventional hematology analyzers, which can cost more than \$200,000. The system's ability to perform CBC analysis remotely offers significant benefits for chronic disease management and monitoring of patients in remote areas, reducing the need for frequent physician visits. This could positively impact providing accessible healthcare in underserved regions and improving patient outcomes through continuous monitoring.

B. Cellytics NK Platform

One notable application of LIST is the Cellytics NK platform.^[124] The Cellytics NK platform is a novel immunodiagnostic platform that utilizes LIST to assess natural killer (NK) cell activity. This platform integrates an NK-specific activation stimulator cocktail (ASC) with LIST to analyze the morphological changes in NK cells after activation. Examining these changes, the platform can accurately distinguish between active and inactive NK cells. As shown in Figure 12A, Cellytics' NK platform involves several key steps: (1) collection of whole blood samples, (2) isolation of primary NK cells, (3) incubation with or without ASC, and (4) analysis of the cells with LIST. The ASC contains IL-2, IL-12, PMA, and ionomycin, which promote NK cells' proliferation, growth, and cytotoxicity.

The LIST technology of Cellytics' NK platform captures hologram images of both resting and activated NK cells. These images are then analyzed by an algorithm that evaluates cell size and cytoplasmic complexity based on shadow parameters. The platform can accurately identify active NK cells by comparing the morphological differences between activated and non-activated cells within 30 s. Figure 12B shows the morphological changes observed in NK cells after activation. The representative cytospin images and flow cytometric analysis show increased cell size and internal complexity (granularity) in activated NK cells. In addition, a comparison of microscopic and shadow images shows apparent morphological differences between activated and non-activated cells.

Cellytics' NK platform also quantifies NK cell activity using an innate immunity index (I^3). This index is calculated based on morphological changes observed in NK cells and correlates strongly with NK cell activity markers such as IFN- γ , TNF- α , perforin, granzyme B, and CD107a. Figure 12C shows a group-wise comparison of the IFN- γ levels measured by ELISA with the I^3 values measured by Cellytics NK. The results show a strong correlation between the two measurements, confirming the validity of the I^3 index as an indicator of NK cell activity.

Cellytics' NK platform offers several advantages over conventional methods for assessing NK cell activity. It is a fast, sensitive, non-invasive method requiring only a small blood sample. In addition, the platform can be used to monitor NK cell activity in real time, making it a valuable tool for research and clinical applications. However, it should be noted that the Cellytics NK platform is still under development, and further studies are needed to establish a standardized reference range for the I^3 index. Nevertheless, the platform is a promising tool for assessing immune function and potentially for the early detection of cancer.

Figure 12. Schematic of the Cellytics NK platform, a single-cell immunodiagnostic system that uses lensless imaging technology to monitor natural killer (NK) cell activity. The platform compares NK cells incubated with or without an NK-specific activation stimulator cocktail (ASC). B. Morphological changes of peripheral NK cells (pNK) after activation. (a) Hema-3-stained cytopspins of NK cells with and without ASC. (b) Flow cytometric analysis of the size and complexity of NK cells after incubation. (c) Comparison of microscopic and shadow images of non-activated and activated NK cells, respectively. (d) Combined shadow parameters for non-activated and activated cells, with statistical significance (* $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$). Adapted with permission from [124]. Copyright 2024 Elsevier.

C. High-Throughput Analysis with Compact and Portable Design

LIST's ability to achieve subcellular resolution over a large FOV enables high-throughput analysis of samples such as blood smears and tissue sections.^[125,126] The ability of this system to accurately count and differentiate blood cells has been validated in comparison to standard hematology analyzers. High correlation indices have been demonstrated for various blood cell types, including red and white blood cells and subpopulations such as neutrophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes.^[127–129] The compact design of the LIST systems, which weigh approximately 46 grams and measure $4.2 \times 4.2 \times 5.8$ cm, makes them particularly suitable for telemedicine applications in resource-constrained environments and offers a portable and cost-effective alternative to bulky and expensive optical microscopes.^[130] Saeki et al. presented a novel digital cell counting method combining a single-cell array with a CMOS sensor.^[131] This single-cell array consists of a microcavity array that can trap up to 7,500 individual cells on a metal

substrate by applying negative pressure. Cell counting uses the shadow images method, in which the light diffraction patterns generated by the microcavity array and the trapped cells make the microcavities occupied by the cells visible as shadow patterns. The CMOS sensor records these patterns and enables digital counting of the cells. The device demonstrated efficient uptake and imaging of unlabeled HeLa cells over a large FOV (30 mm²) within 160 s. The results showed a strong linear correlation ($r^2 = 0.99$) with conventional microscopic observations, indicating high accuracy. The system is effective at extremely low cell concentrations of 25 to 15,000 cells/mL, making it suitable for routine laboratory use. In addition, some lensless microscopes have a dual-mode design that enables both transmission and reflection imaging, further increasing their versatility and usefulness in telemedicine.^[132]

D. Advanced Imaging Capabilities

The versatility of LIST is also demonstrated by its ability to perform differential interference contrast imaging and color imaging using computational methods. These capabilities are crucial for various diagnostic applications, such as detecting malaria parasites and analyzing Pap smear samples.^[133] For example, Oh et al. integrated a birefringent crystal with lensless digital holography to develop an on-chip microscope with differential interference contrast (DIC) (Figure 13A).^[134] The study explores a technique to recover the 2D phase information of a complex optical field that is generally lost during the detection process in lensless DIC microscopy. By utilizing the amplitudes of lensless holograms and applying an iterative phase recovery algorithm, the researchers effectively remove the twin image artifact that is critical for improving contrast in DIC images. This backpropagation of the recovered fields enables the generation of DIC images that reveal subtle micro-object features, such as surface relief and shadow effects characteristic of DIC operation.

Figure 13B compares DIC images obtained with conventional DIC microscopy and the lensless holographic DIC microscope for different samples. The results show that the lensless holographic approach provides better contrast and less distortion, resulting in clearer imaging of *C. elegans* specimens, 5 and 10 μm diameter particles, and white blood cells in blood smears. This improvement surpasses the contrast achieved with conventional brightfield microscopy.

Other applications include the automatic analysis of blood counts,^[135,136] the assessment of cell viability,^[137] and 3D cell tomography.^[138,139] An artificial intelligence (AI)- supported automatic signal enhancement process significantly improves these analyses' accuracy. It achieves an accuracy of over 98% in identifying and counting red and white blood cells.^[80,123,140] In addition, a compact and cost-effective lensless CMOS image sensor was developed to detect bacterial cells in enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA). This platform outperforms commercial ELISA readers in detecting pathogenic bacteria such as *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella typhimurium* in a 96-well plate format.^[141]

Figure 13. (A) Schematic representation of the lensless holographic differential interference contrast microscope (DIC). (B) Comparison of DIC images obtained with conventional DIC microscopy and lensless holographic DIC microscopy for different specimens. (C) Experimental setup for lensless analysis of clinical CSF samples. The optical setup includes multispectral illumination by an RGB multi-quadrant LED connected to a $150 \mu\text{m}$ pinhole via a 60° diffuser. The CMOS sensor records red, green, and blue holograms in sequence. (D) Scatter plot of lensless images of leukocytes and erythrocytes from 116 clinical samples in the feasibility study. Lensless microscopy achieved a sensitivity of 100% and a specificity of 79% for diagnosing infectious meningitis. (A), (B) Reproduced under terms of the CC-BY license from [134]. Copyright 2010 Optica Publishing Group. (C), (D) Adapted with permission from [142]. Copyright 2017 Springer Nature.

E. Innovations in Diagnostic Platforms

The integration of lensless holographic imaging with antibody microarrays has proven to be a powerful tool for analyzing leukocytes and cytokines in human blood. It provides markers such as the CD4/CD8 ratio for HIV/AIDS diagnostics.^[143] This approach improves the performance of on-chip cytometry by enabling faster and more sensitive detection without conventional lenses or microscope objectives.^[20] In addition, a lensless 3D imaging platform has been developed for non-invasive visualization of single cells and tissues, enabling in vivo studies of complex biological processes without disturbing their natural state.^[139,144] In a notable study by Delacroix et al., LIST was investigated for its potential to support the diagnosis of meningitis by counting leukocytes and erythrocytes in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF).^[142] This system was based on the multi-wavelength detection setup described by Seo et al., with a Cree MC-E Color Quadrant RGB LED providing illumination at different wavelengths (Figure 13C)⁵³. An algorithm for automatically counting leukocytes and erythrocytes in cerebrospinal fluid samples was developed to facilitate the early diagnosis of meningitis.

In the study, 215 CSF samples were analyzed, including both infectious and non-infectious meningitis cases. Initial testing showed considerable inter-user variability in light microscopy, resulting in 16.7% of samples being misclassified. Lensless microscopy showed improved diagnostic accuracy, with a sensitivity of 100% and a specificity of 86% after adjustments to differentiate between leukocytes and erythrocytes. Figure 20D shows a scatter plot of the lensless counting leukocytes and erythrocytes in 116 CSF samples. In a blind test with 116 CSF samples, the sensitivity remained 100%, while the specificity was slightly lower at 79%. LFI systematically overestimates the leukocyte count compared to optical microscopy. The linear correlation between the two methods for cell concentrations up to 5.10^4 cells/ μL underlines their reliability. This advance highlights the potential of lensless microscopy as a rapid, operator-independent diagnostic tool, particularly for POC applications where it could significantly improve diagnostic workflows for diseases such as meningitis.

4.5. Microfluidics and Lensless Imaging Integration

Integrating microfluidics with LIST has proven to be a powerful approach for improving the sensitivity, accuracy, and versatility of diagnostic and cellular analysis applications. In microfluidics, small volumes of liquid are manipulated in microscopic channels, enabling continuous and automated sample handling.^[145,146] This capability enables high-throughput analysis in conjunction with LIST, which is critical for various applications such as POC diagnostics and environmental monitoring.^[147–152] One of the main advantages is the development of compact, stand-alone biosensor systems that can perform multiple analyses simultaneously, drastically reducing the time required for diagnostic procedures.^[153] These systems are characterized by low operating costs, which ensures their accessibility and applicability in various clinical and research environments.^[148,152] Such compact biosensor platforms are particularly valuable in environments that require rapid diagnostics, such as clinical laboratories and disease outbreak investigations.

A. Enhancements in POC Diagnostics

Several research groups have investigated the feasibility of integrating microfluidics with LIST for POC diagnostics.^[154] For example, it has been shown that integrating LIST into microfluidic systems can improve high-throughput label-free imaging flow cytometry. Barroso et al. investigated the integration of LIST into microfluidic systems to improve high-throughput label-free flow cytometry.^[155] The study focuses on the characterization of microfluidic systems where hydrodynamic focusing is used to precisely control the flow of sample fluids, which is critical for accurately monitoring and analyzing microscopic particles such as cells. Figure 14A shows the microfluidic chip used in the study, which is equipped with hydrodynamic focusing to ensure that the particles in the sample fluid are directed into the field of view for imaging. Figure 14B illustrates the influence of different sheath fluid-to-sample fluid ratios on the width of the sample stream and its effect on imaging quality in lensless imaging systems. The sheath fluid surrounding the sample fluid plays a decisive role in the narrowing of the sample stream. However, a higher sheath-to-sample ratio can lead to excessively narrow streams, resulting in blurred images if the exposure time of the CMOS sensor is not correctly calibrated. This study emphasizes that an optimal sheath-to-sample ratio is critical to the quality of quantitative phase imaging (QPI) in LI to ensure accurate and clear imaging results.

On the other hand, a ratio of less than 4:1 can cause the sample flow to exceed the FOV, resulting in incomplete capture of the particle population and potentially compromising the imaging process. The ability to adjust the width of the focused sample stream ensures that

all particles, especially cells, are within the FOV, allowing for comprehensive and high-resolution imaging.

Figure 14C shows the results of holographic particle image velocimetry (HPIV) using LIST to characterize the fluid flow in the microfluidic channel. The study indicates that LIST can accurately track the trajectories of particles, making it a valuable tool for analyzing fluid dynamics in microfluidic systems. Using different pump settings, LFI effectively analyzes live cells in hydrodynamically focused sample streams, proving particularly useful for applications such as cell counting and biomarker detection — crucial factors for POC diagnostic procedures. This demonstrates the system's versatility in monitoring live cells without fluorescent labeling, increasing its utility in clinical and field-based diagnostics.

B. Particle Tracking Innovations

In particle tracking, Di et al. investigated using a compact LI microscope to measure microparticles in suspension, focusing specifically on particles in the micrometer range.^[156] Similarly, Cheong et al. utilized lensless video microscopy to track and characterize colloidal particles in three dimensions, achieving nanometer-scale precision.^[157] This technique uses video streams to estimate particle size and refractive index using a nonlinear Levenberg-Marquardt least-squares fitting algorithm, which ensures accurate parameter estimation and enables automated, unsupervised particle tracking.

The researchers applied this approach to visualize the flow dynamics in a microfluidic channel. They tracked the trajectories of 500 individual polystyrene spheres, revealing a parabolic flow profile characteristic of Poiseuille flow in such systems. As shown in Figure 14D, the lineage forest visualization elucidates the complexity of lensless microscopy for cell detection. This method is particularly advantageous for detecting subtle variations in particle properties, including size and refractive index, even in dynamic environments, increasing its potential for high-precision analysis in real-time applications.

Rempfler et al. presented a new framework for cell lineage tracking that focuses on developing a cell recognition system based on fully convolutional networks and residual learning.^[158] A vital framework component is a probabilistic model based on moral lineage tracing to manage multiple detections and temporal successor hypotheses. With this model, cells are clustered and tracked simultaneously, improving the accuracy of cell lineage estimation. They constructed a spatio-temporal hypothesis graph to represent cell probability maps, critical for detecting cell centers in each sequence image. Experiments with skin cancer cell lines revealed differences in growth rates and motility between populations exposed to inhibitor and control groups. The study compares the performance of different detectors, including Resnet-23, UNet, and CNN-4, regarding precision, recognition value, and F1 score. Figure 14E compares the performance of the different detectors (Resnet-23, UNet, CNN-4) regarding the precision, recall, and F1 score for cell detection. The results show that Resnet-23 is the most robust detector, followed by UNet and CNN-4. Figure 14F shows the average performance metrics obtained for a fluorescence-annotated dataset. The study introduces a novel method based on the moral lineage analysis problem and compares its performance with the disjoint trees problem. MLTP consistently achieves better precision, recall, and F1-score results, indicating its superior performance in cell lineage tracing. Retraining detectors to fluorescence-based annotations improves their performance, especially for sequences with high cell culture density. This retraining helps the models to learn more sophisticated annotations and improves their ability to discriminate cells in close proximity. This research makes an essential

contribution to the field by providing a robust tool for analyzing time-lapse image sequences in LFM, offering valuable insights into cell growth, migration, and related biological processes.^[159]

Figure 14. (A) (a) Microfluidic chip on a microscope stage for measuring fluid flows. (b) Rectangular microchannel with hydrodynamic focusing, where the sheath fluid controls the width of the sample fluid for optimized imaging. (B) Comparison of particle stream width at different sheath-to-sample ratios: (a) 7:1 and (b) 10:1. (c) Diagram showing the variation of particle stream width perpendicular to the flow, with $405 \mu\text{m}$ at 7:1 and $290 \mu\text{m}$ at 10:1. (C) Holographic particle image velocimetry shows the 3D trajectories of 500 independent $1 \mu\text{m}$ polystyrene spheres flowing through a microfluidic channel, illustrating label-free flow analysis. (D) Visualization of cell lineage tracing with LFI. The top section shows a lineage forest where individual trees are color-coded to represent different cell lineages over time. (E) Performance comparison of different cell recognition detectors based on precision, recall and F1 score as evaluated on the original test datasets by Rempfler et al. (2017). Boxplots show the median (orange line), mean (black square) and outliers (gray +). Resnet-23 proves to be the most robust detector and achieves an average F1 value of 94.1 %, followed by UNet (89.2 %), Resnet-11 (85.1 %) and CNN-4 (72.2 %). (F) Average performance metrics obtained with the fluorescence dataset. All metrics are expressed as percentages, with averages calculated for all sequences and reported in the last row. MLTP shows superior performance across different detectors, highlighting the benefits of retraining to fluorescence-based annotations, especially in high cell culture density scenarios. (A), (B), (C) Adapted with permission from ^[155]. Copyright 2010 SPIE. (D), (E), (F) Adapted with permission from ^[158]. Copyright 2018 Elsevier.

C. Applications in Bioimaging

LIST has been successfully integrated into microfluidic systems for various applications, including measuring three-dimensional flows in a T-shaped micromixer,^[160] improving quantitative analysis,^[161] optofluidic tomography,^[162] and bioimaging. These integrations are

crucial for bioimaging applications as they enable detailed analysis at the micro level.^[163] For example, Huang et al. have developed an innovative platform that combines optoelectronic tweezers (OET) with lensless microscopy to manipulate cells and microparticles on a chip.^[164] Figure 15A shows a schematic diagram of the experimental setup, highlighting the main components and the optical configuration. The OET system utilizes light-induced dielectrophoretic forces to manipulate particles, while the lensless microscope enables high-resolution imaging and tracking. When a beam of light is projected onto an OET device, it creates additional electrons and holes, increasing the local light conductivity. This makes virtual electrodes and non-uniform electric fields that enable manipulating cells and particles. Light sources, including laser beams, can trigger and pattern virtual electrodes on an OET platform. By integrating lensless holographic imaging with OET, the study overcomes the FOV limitations of conventional optical systems. This integration enables the interactive manipulation of thousands of single cells and microparticles in real time over an extremely large area, e.g., 240 mm². Figure 15B provides a comprehensive overview of the capabilities of the OET system and shows a full-view holographic image that enables interactive manipulation of 901 target particles. Figure 15B (a) shows the initial configuration, while panel 15B (b) shows a detailed magnification of the manipulation process. The successive snapshots in Figure 15B (c–f) show how selected particles can be aligned to form an elliptical pattern and illustrate the system's efficiency in tracking and manipulating micro-objects in real time. The platform uses light-induced dielectrophoretic forces to move cells and particles and has a closed feedback loop for dynamic tracking and manipulation. This approach supports various biological applications such as blood analysis and fertility testing by providing a programmable and parallel manipulation capability with an extensive range of action.

Figure 15. A) Schematic diagram of the optoelectronic tweezers (OET) experimental setup with integrated lensless microscopy. The diagram illustrates the operating principle of the OET, in which light-induced dielectrophoretic forces manipulate cells and microparticles on a photoconductive substrate by generating virtual electrodes and non-uniform electric fields. (B) (a) Full FOV image showing the parallel manipulation of 901 target particles in the OET system. (b) Magnified image of a panel (a) showing detailed interactions. (c–f) Sequential snapshots showing the programmed manipulation of selected particles from a random population into an elliptical formation. The arrows indicate the direction and final destination of the target particles, while the light spots in panels (c) and (d) illustrate the tracking and manipulation of micro-objects by the OET system. Adapted with permission from ^[164]. Copyright 2013 Royal Society of Chemistry.

4.6. Integration with Smartphone Platforms

Integrating smartphones into LIST can be a revolutionary tool for biosensing, offering high mobility, cost efficiency, and accessibility. Equipped with high-resolution cameras, powerful processors, and wireless connectivity, smartphones provide an ideal platform for these systems. Typically, a compact, lensless imaging module is connected to the smartphone camera, which contains a light source and a sample holder. After illumination, the smartphone camera

captures the diffraction pattern of the sample, and specialized applications process these patterns to reconstruct images. This conversion allows smartphones to be used as high-throughput portable imaging devices suitable for various analyses, from pathogen detection in biological samples to identifying contaminants in water.^[116,165]

A. Advantages of Integration

One of the main advantages of integrating LIST into smartphones lies in the high-resolution sensors and integrated lighting of smartphone cameras, which provide high-quality images that can be used to detect microscopic particles.^[166] Smartphones' widespread use and user-friendly interfaces make LIST integration an accessible and convenient platform for biosensor technology. Integrating machine learning (ML) into smartphone-based holographic microscopy further advances these systems and enables the automatic classification of microparticles — a crucial capability for environmental monitoring.^[165,167] Such systems have demonstrated high accuracy in particle size classification, highlighting their potential for mobile healthcare and environmental applications.^[168]

B. Portable Digital Lensless Holographic Microscope

Acosta et al. developed a portable digital lensless holographic microscope specifically designed for use in the field.^[169] This system features a customized illumination device with a free-form lens housed in a 3D-printed tube to facilitate alignment. The compact prototype, with a height of 13.6 cm and a weight of 250 g, uses a HUAWEI P8 Lite smartphone sensor to capture holograms with magnifications from 1× to 20× and a resolution of 1.71 μm. Other approaches use 3D printing to construct the optical system, paired with Android applications for real-time hologram reconstruction, enabling 3D imaging and interactive zoom capabilities through smartphone gestures.^[170] In addition, systems built with low-cost components such as coherent laser beams and pinholes integrated into smartphone cameras offer wide FOV imaging and high spatial resolution while being portable and lightweight.^[167]

C. Recent Advancements

Recent advances in smartphone-based LI systems include the combination of lensless and lens-based microscopy for accurate color imaging over a large FOV.^[171] This is achieved by wavelet-based image fusion algorithms that improve imaging capabilities. In addition, LFI microscopes with off-axis transmission have simplified computational methods and enable real-time phase imaging with smartphone processors. These systems are cost-effective and suitable for educational purposes, further increasing their accessibility.^[172]

Smartphone-based LI systems have proven their worth in detecting malaria parasites in blood samples and monitoring cell cultures in remote locations.^[173] In environmental science, these systems are used to monitor water quality by detecting pollutants or microorganisms, and their portability enables on-site testing and instant analysis, which is crucial for timely environmental management decisions.^[174] Ongoing advances in microfabrication and computational algorithms are expected to further enhance these systems, with innovations such as multi-pixel height super-resolution and improved light sources increasing image resolution and accuracy.^[175] In addition, the development of more user-friendly applications and interfaces makes these systems accessible to non-experts, which increases their impact. Integrating ML algorithms could automate image analysis, improve diagnostic accuracy and speed, and expand the application possibilities of LI systems integrated into smartphones.^[93]

4.7. Cancer Diagnostics

LFI has become an important tool in cancer diagnostics, with applications ranging from early detection and treatment monitoring to studies on the behavior of cancer cells⁷⁷.

A. Early Detection and Imaging

Early detection plays a critical role in improving treatment outcomes, particularly in oncology, and lensless holography has shown promise in detecting cellular morphologic changes indicative of cancer. In a critical study by Greenbaum et al., LI was used to image cervical cancer cells using a computerized on-chip holographic microscope combining the transport-of-intensity equation (TIE), iterative phase recovery at multiple heights, and rotating field transformations.^[176] This technique enabled imaging with a large FOV, which is crucial for analyzing pathology samples. In the study, TIE was used with a finite element method-based elliptic equation solver, which provides higher accuracy than the FFT-based approach, although the latter is computationally faster. This method allowed digital focusing at any depth within the sample's FOV without mechanical adjustments. It also corrected for artifacts caused by tilt and height differences between the sample and sensor planes, which improved image quality.

Greenbaum et al. examined various pathology samples, including invasive carcinoma cells in human breast tissue sections, Papanicolaou smears of high-grade squamous cell carcinoma, and blood smears of sickle cell anemia, all through a 20.5 mm² FOV. The images generated with this technique provided sufficient resolution and contrast for clinical assessment and achieved an impressive diagnostic accuracy of approximately 99% in a blinded study conducted by a pathologist. This high accuracy highlights the potential of lensless holography as a powerful tool for early disease detection, particularly in cancer diagnostics, where it could offer significant advantages in early detection and monitoring at the time of treatment.

B. Intraoperative Pathology

Intraoperative pathology is another area where lensless holography has shown promise. Conventional pathology often requires time-consuming staining procedures, delaying critical surgical decisions. A new lensless holography technique solves these problems by eliminating the need for staining, reducing specimen processing time, and enabling faster diagnoses. Morel et al. present a LIST to improve intraoperative pathology by allowing rapid and detailed imaging of unstained tissue sections.^[177] The system captures single-shot RGB holograms over a large FOV of 10 mm² to 6 cm² in a multispectral recording device that simultaneously records holograms at three wavelengths.

The fabric carrier is moved across the sensor in an XY pattern while recording 9.7 mm² RGB holograms at each position. Up to 80 RGB holograms can be recorded in just 12 min, underlining the efficiency of the process. These holograms are then computationally reconstructed into phase images, with the reconstruction time for a 500 mm² area on a CPU being around 20 minutes and even faster when using a graphics processor. The reconstructed images, which achieve a resolution of 2 to 3 μm, are sufficiently detailed to visualize individual cells and identify regions of interest within the tissue sample.

In addition, the method enables the imaging of entire tissue sections by capturing multiple holograms and stitching them together to form a mosaic, creating a comprehensive reconstructed image of 25 x 25 mm². The study also demonstrated the technique's effectiveness

by comparing the LI results with conventional hematoxylin-eosin-saffron-stained slides. It was found that the structural information of the tissue can be further enhanced by calculating the local variance over the reconstructed phase images, allowing better visualization of cellular structures. This cost-effective and compact system is particularly beneficial during intraoperative consultations as it supports quick surgical decisions by providing timely insights into lesions and tumor margins.

C. Molecular Profiling

LIST has shown significant potential for molecular profiling, mainly through platforms such as the digital diffraction diagnostics (D3) system, which uses smartphone-based technology for molecular and cellular diagnostics.^[178] This system can detect object concentrations of four orders of magnitude and process up to 10^8 microbeads or cells per milliliter of sample, making it suitable for high-throughput applications.

Figure 16A shows the D3 system, which uses streptavidin-coated microbeads to generate characteristic diffraction patterns recorded by a smartphone camera. The system consists of an attachable module with an LED for illumination, a pinhole to achieve partial coherence, and a sample holder for optimal positioning of the samples. This configuration enables the effective acquisition of unique diffraction patterns from the microbeads. Figure 17B illustrates the workflow of the D3 system. The camera integrated into the smartphone captures diffraction images of the samples, which are then transmitted to a remote server equipped with GPU technology. This setup enables massively parallel image processing, resulting in significantly faster image reconstruction and analysis than conventional CPU-based systems. The D3 system can deliver diagnostic results in near real-time, typically within two minutes, demonstrating its potential for rapid diagnosis.

Figure 16. (A) Overview of the smartphone module of the D3 system, which consists of a coin-battery powered LED, a pinhole to achieve uniform illumination with partial coherence, and a sample holder. This configuration enables the recording of diffraction patterns generated by streptavidin-coated microbeads on a smartphone camera. (B) Image of the smartphone's integrated camera mounted on the D3 capturing diffraction images of the sample. These images are then transmitted to a remote server via a cloud service for real-time image reconstruction and analysis, with results typically returned to the smartphone in less than 2 min. (C) Detection of cancer cell markers using immunobead labeling. Human breast carcinoma cells (SkBr3) were labeled with immunobeads targeting HER2, EpCAM, and EGFR. The top row shows reconstructed images in pseudocolors (green for transmittance; red for phase). The middle row shows corresponding brightfield images, while the bottom row shows fluorescently labeled antibodies for comparison. Labels: HER2, human epidermal growth factor receptor 2; EpCAM, epithelial cell adhesion molecule; EGFR, epidermal growth factor receptor. (D) Comparison of bead counts on labeled cells determined with the D3 system with manual counts from microscope images, which show a high agreement with an R^2 value of 0.97, demonstrating the reliability of automatic bead counting. (E) The correlation between the average bead count per cell and the expression level of target markers determined by flow cytometry with an R^2 value of 0.99 indicates a strong relationship. Labels: MFI,

mean fluorescence intensity; a.u., arbitrary units. Adapted with permission from ^[178]. Copyright 2015 National Academy of Sciences.

The study showed that microbeads, combined with biotinylated antibodies, can efficiently bind to the target cells and improve detection sensitivity. Different bead sizes were tested, with diameters between 5 and 7 μm proving optimal for accurate bead counting and reducing cell clustering. Figure 16C illustrates the efficacy of immunobead labeling in detecting cancer cell markers on SkBr3 cells. The top row shows reconstructed pseudocolor images that clearly show the binding of the microbeads to the target cells. The middle and bottom rows consist of brightfield micrographs and fluorescent antibody labeling, respectively, and provide a comprehensive overview of the experimental setup and results. Figure 16D shows the automatic bead counting of the D3 system, which correlates very well with the manual counts from conventional microscope images, yielding an R^2 value of 0.97. This high correlation demonstrates the robustness and reliability of the D3 system in quantifying microbeads. Figure 16E illustrates the strong correlation between the average number of beads per cell and the expression values of the target markers determined by flow cytometry, with an R^2 value of 0.99 being achieved. These data emphasize the sensitivity and accuracy of the D3 system in assessing cancer cell markers and confirm its potential as a valuable diagnostic tool in the clinical setting.

In addition to cervical cancer, the D3 system has been adapted for detecting lymphoma cells in fine needle aspirates, demonstrating its versatility in various malignancies. Notably, the system supports quantitative and operator-independent analysis, detecting the number of cells and the expression levels of molecular markers. This feature represents a significant advance in POC diagnostics as it ensures consistency and reproducibility across different users and environments.

D. Advances in Deep Learning

Recent advances have integrated deep learning into lensless holography to improve its diagnostic capabilities, particularly in cancer diagnostics.^[179] For example, Song et al. presented HoloNet, a deep learning architecture developed specifically for analyzing holograms from LIST.^[180] HoloNet efficiently extracts cellular hologram features that accurately classify breast cancer cell types and estimate intensity values for key markers such as ER/PR and HER2. This system optimizes breast cancer cell analysis by enabling direct classification of cells from raw holograms using CNNs.

Building on this, the researchers used deep transfer learning to improve cell analysis in holograms.^[181] A pre-trained VGG19 model was used to extract features from holograms, which was combined with principal component analysis and a multilayer perceptron to improve performance. This approach proved robust even on noisy data and outperformed conventional classifiers such as support vector machines and random forests on both two- and five-class classifications.^[180]

Several excellent recent review articles on integrating deep learning and LIST exist.^[182-187] Integrating deep learning with LIST provides a noninvasive, portable, and cost-effective method for cancer diagnostics, with applications in early cancer detection, treatment monitoring, and the study of cancer cell behavior. In addition, the combination of deep learning and smartphone technology expands the potential of LIST, making it a valuable tool in modern medical diagnostics and increasing access to advanced diagnostic tools. Table 1 summarizes the important studies showing the application of LIST in various biosensor tasks, such as cell

analysis, pathogen detection, and biomolecular assays. The table highlights specific applications, contributions to the field, and the potential impact of each study.

Table 1. Summary of recent advances in LIST for biosensing applications

Ref.	Applications	Contributions
[124]	Rapid and precise measurement of NK cell activity.	Can distinguish active NK cells from inactive NK cells at the single cell level within 30 s by assessing cell size and cytoplasmic complexity based on shadow parameters derived from digital hologram images acquired with LIST
[185]	Cell monitoring	Demonstration of a high-throughput continuous cell monitoring technique that can monitor more than 6,000 human alveolar epithelial cells simultaneously and continuously for up to 48 h with a single 5-megapixel shadow image.
[106]	SARS-CoV-2 detection	Used computational imaging and deep learning to quantify individual microbeads undergoing agglutination, enabling accurate determination of virus concentrations above the LOD of 1.27×10^3 copies per mL.
[186]	Pathology diagnosis	Design and fabrication of a submicron pixel imaging chip with a pixel size of $0.95 \mu\text{m} \times 0.95 \mu\text{m}$ and a pixel count of 25 million ($5120\text{H} \times 5120\text{V}$). Demonstrated full-color shadow microscopy images of tissue samples using trichromatic sequential illumination (627 nm, 530 nm, and 405 nm) acquired with the prototype system.
[187]	LUCAS for high-throughput cell-biology experiments.	This platform can image a heterogeneous cell solution over an ultra-wide field of view of up to $\sim 18 \text{ cm}^2$ without refocusing, covering a depth of field of $\sim 5 \text{ mm}$ and a sample volume of up to $\sim 9 \text{ mL}$. LUCAS records the shadows of the cells in its field of view and enables automated digital processing to determine cell type, number, and relative position.
[60]	Characterization of microparticles and biological cells, including automatic analysis of complete blood count (CBC), cell viability, 2D cell morphology, and 3D cell tomography.	Presents an AI-powered automatic signal enhancement method that uses an autoencoder for noise reduction and adaptive cell characterization by transfer learning to improve LIST for cytometry. Achieved over 98% accuracy and over 5 dB signal enhancement for most cell types, including erythrocytes and leukocytes, allowing the system to adapt and classify new sample types quickly.
[140]	An automated cell detection and counting platform.	Presents an automated method for detecting and counting cells using the adaptive thresholding technique for lensless shadow images that overcomes the limitations of semi-automatic image processing methods and manual threshold selection.
[188]	Differentiation between (RBCs and a tumor cell line	A portable, lensless cell imaging system that utilizes resistive pulses from biological cells in a microfluidic channel. The system

	(HepG2) in a microfluidic channel.	enables dual parametric examination (light contrast image and electrical pulse) for each cell, effectively differentiating between red blood cells and the HepG2 tumor cell line in flow analysis.
[142]	CMOS image sensor-based ELISA detector for blood analysis.	Detection of pathogens, particularly pathogenic bacteria such as <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> and <i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> , in a conventional 96-well plate.
[123]	A compact, cost-effective and automated method for counting blood cells	The proposed device has high correlation indices for erythrocyte, and WBC counts compared to a standard hematology analyzer, indicating its reliability and accuracy in performing the critical elements of CBC. In addition, the system shows potential for telemedicine applications by sending images wirelessly for processing on a smartphone, which improves its accessibility and usability in remote healthcare facilities.
[110]	Detection of nucleic acids, especially DNA fragments	Detection of DNA concentrations up to 10 pM with single particle sensitivity
[127]	WBC classification	Demonstration of the effectiveness of the projection of principal edge distribution algorithm in sorting the three leukocyte subtypes using low-resolution images acquired with a CMOS shadow imaging system, with a correlation of 0.93 between the proposed system and the reference system (BC-5180, Mindray).
[189]	POC measurements of blood flow in biological tissues	presents in vitro data collected on tissue-simulating fluid phantoms and in vivo data collected on human subjects using occlusion protocols, demonstrating the ability of the wearable LIST device to provide both visual and quantitative characterization of regional blood flow, with a particular focus on potential applications in neonatal care.
[190]	Health diagnostics in developing countries, where parasitic infections such as schistosomiasis and malaria are often underdiagnosed.	A low-cost method for producing microlens arrays for microscopy, with lenses having an average diameter of 222 μm and a distance of 300 μm .
[51]	Monitoring platform for determining the CD4 T lymphocyte count in HIV-infected patients	Monitor and count different cell types, such as blood cells, NIH-3T3 fibroblasts, mouse embryonic stem cells, and AML-12 hepatocytes, using the optical approach in combination with microfluidic channels for parallel on-chip monitoring.
[191]	Normalized cross-correlation (NCC) is applied to detect cell-like objects in blood images.	The proposed NCC-CNN system showed the highest accuracy (96.7-98.4%) in counting different types of blood cells and outperformed other algorithms in accurately analyzing noisy blood images by up to 36.8. In addition, the time required for cell counting was significantly reduced, making it 24.0-40.8 times faster than other methods.

[98]	Automatic urinalysis at the patient's bedside is intended to enable early detection of UTI and other pathological processes at the site of occurrence.	Able to resolve important clinical biomarkers in urine such as red blood cells, white blood cells, crystals, and deposits in 2 mm thick urine phantoms.
[55]	High-throughput continuous cell monitoring	Simultaneously and continuously monitoring more than 6000 human alveolar epithelial A549 cells for up to 72 h without labeling reagents or destroying samples.
[128]	Portable leukocyte classification,	Several shadow parameters, such as the 'order ratio' and the 'minimum ratio', were defined to identify the type of leukocytes. With these parameters, the three leukocyte types could be classified with a correlation index of 0.98 compared to clinical reference data, with an average error of 6% and a confidence level of 95%.
[192]	Rapid detection of biomarkers, e.g., for sepsis and potentially other diseases such as cancer.	Simultaneous analysis of up to 10,000 functionalized microarray spots with different biomarkers provides fast results in a few minutes and consumes a small sample volume ($\sim 10 \mu\text{L}$).
[137]	Measurement of cell viability without the use of staining reagents.	Cell viability without needing staining reagents enables the immediate assessment of more than 3000 human cancer cells with a single digital image.
[193]	Non-invasive recording of in-vitro cell deformation in cardiac monolayers with high temporal (169 fps) and spatial resolution (352 μm) over a FOV of up to 57 mm^2 .	Can detect impairment of both contractility and fast excitation waves in cardiac monolayers, providing multiparametric information on cardiac cells for a more in-depth analysis of drug-induced effects in preclinical cardiotoxicity screening applications.
[194]	Monitoring and characterization of different cell types in a heterogeneous solution	Fast monitoring and characterization of different cell types in a heterogeneous solution with a depth of field of about 4 mm and a field of view of about 10 cm^2 . It uses a custom algorithm to identify and localize microparticle types within a sample volume by analyzing their unique diffraction patterns. Using statistical image libraries and digital processing, heterogeneous microobjects, including red blood cells, hepatocytes, yeast cells, and microspheres in multilayered samples, are accurately counted and characterized.
[195]	Determination of parvovirus B19 DNA with immobilized oligonucleotide probe microarrays	Combines a transparent, microfluidic-based reaction chip with a thermoelectrically cooled CCD sensor, enabling quantitatively detecting analytes with high sensitivity and a wide dynamic range. Achieve high signal detectability, a wide dynamic range, and detection limits down to attomole levels of proteins and femtomole levels of nucleic acid analytes.

[60]	Characterization of microparticles and biological cells, including automated analysis of CBC, cell viability, 2D cell morphology, and 3D cell tomography.	Development of an automatic characterization algorithm based on artificial intelligence techniques, such as denoising autoencoder and adaptive cell characterization using deep neural networks, significantly improving signal quality and enabling accurate classification of cell types such as RBCs and WBCs with an accuracy of over 98%.
[196]	label-free blood smear imaging.	High-resolution imaging capabilities and the ability to capture detailed information from blood smears without labeling or staining.
[197]	Low-cost telemedical device for the automatic measurement of cell and particle sizes	Can detect and measure the size of multiple micro-objects, such as polystyrene microspheres and various biological cells simultaneously, in a single digital image with a maximum resolution of 2 mm at a cost of less than 100 USD and in a short time (within 1 min).
[84]	Seawater toxicity monitoring	D. tertiolecta was categorized into live (healthy and cystic) and dead cells based on the shadow parameter CMV and into healthy and cystic cells based on the shadow parameter SMD with 95% confidence. This bioassay technology has shown that 20 out of 30 HNS can be tested for toxicity in less than 5 min based on the morphological ratio (circular ratio) at EC50.
[198]	label-free identification of CD34+ cells in leukemia patients.	Development of a custom AlexNet deep learning model that achieves high accuracy in identifying CD34+ cells from bone marrow cell images, with training and validation accuracies of 97.3% and 96.2%, respectively.
[199]	Detection of microbes	Non-invasive detection of bacteria in situ in environmental samples from the deep sea (Lo'ihlhi Seamount)
[102]	Detection of pathogenic bacteria species.	A two-stage deep learning architecture that integrates detection and classification networks for real-time detection and identification of pathogenic bacterial colonies using lensless microscopy time-lapse. The detection network achieved an average detection rate 96.0 at T = 8 h, tested on 1,908 colonies of seven different species. The classification network showed an average precision and sensitivity of 93.1 % and 94.0 %, respectively, with perfect results for E. faecalis and a high result of 99.7 % for S. epidermidis, also tested on 1,908 colonies.
[200]	Real-time images of various tissue samples	An embedded, computerized LFI system that enables real-time imaging of medical specimens.
[201]	Tuberculosis diagnostics	investigates the microscopic observation of drug susceptibility tests and an LIST system to diagnose tuberculosis. The test is based on identifying characteristic attachment patterns of Mycobacterium tuberculosis in liquid cultures, typically observed between 7 and 10 days after culture.

[97]	Stain-free quantitative viral plaque assay	The device automatically detected the first cell lysis events due to viral replication as early as five hours after incubation. It achieved a detection rate of >90 for plaque-forming units (PFUs) with 100 % specificity in <20 h for VSV and reduced the incubation time by ~48 hours for HSV-1 and ~20 h for EMCV.
[202]	Disease diagnostics	Produced images comparable to a conventional brightfield microscope at 400x magnification, using infrared and blue laser diodes to image blood smears. The blue light source provided clearer results when imaging red blood cells, which are more abundant in a blood film than white blood cells.
[203]	Automated micro-object detection	An automated method for detecting micro-objects that shows a strong correlation with the results of a standard optical microscope (correlation coefficient of 0.91, linearity slope of 0.877). The algorithm effectively counts and analyzes micro-objects such as polystyrene microbeads, red blood cells, and various cell types.
[204]	LIST-based on spatially resolved nano-illumination instead of spatially resolved detection.	Uses a GaN chip with an 8x8 array of 5 μm LEDs and a commercially available CMOS image sensor with an integrated lens for image reconstruction. The study evaluated image quality based on contrast and structure similarity index and found that larger sensor areas integrate environmental information, which affects image reconstruction
[205]	Bacteria and bacteriophage lysis	A portable 3D-printed reader detects bacteria's lytic fragmentation and determines the host specificity of bacteriophages with a sensitivity comparable to that of spectrophotometers. The system visualizes lysis and measures bacterial concentrations to 8×10^4 CFU per microdevice, demonstrating the potential for rapid detection.
[206]	Micro-algae flocculation analysis	This is a novel real-time method for detecting individual cells and flocs based on parameters such as floc number, area, and size.
[207]	Cell viability	Live imaging method for in situ quantification of neutral red uptake (NRUA) demonstrated on HepG2 cells, highlighting the cost-effective potential for screening conditions that promote 3D growth.
[208]	E.coli and Bacillus subtilis bacteria	LIST using a thin wetting film significantly improved the signal-to-noise ratio and enabled the detection of micro-objects with a strong signal, such as E. coli, Bacillus subtilis bacteria, and 1 μm polymer beads. The technique exhibited a detection efficiency of 85 ± 7 % and a co-localization error of $\sigma_{1D} = 1.1$ μm , making it a promising pre-positioning tool for optical identification methods such as Raman spectroscopy.

[35]	High-resolution imaging capabilities for blood smears	Imaging of blood smears, particularly for diagnosing diseases such as malaria and sickle cell anemia, and in imaging histopathological specimens to detect early signs of breast cancer.
[209]	Virtual staining of sperm cells	Introduces HoloStain, which converts holographic images of unstained cells into virtually stained images, providing a non-toxic, efficient, and consistent alternative to conventional staining methods. Demonstrated the application of HoloStain to human sperm cells, a critical area where staining is not permitted during in vitro fertilization due to potential cytotoxicity.

5. Challenges and Future Directions

LIST is an innovative technique promising in various fields, such as biomedical diagnostics, environmental monitoring, and food safety. This technology offers advantages such as cost efficiency, portability, and the ability to capture large fields of view without complex optical components. However, some challenges must be overcome to fully exploit this technology's potential.

5.1 Challenges

5.1.1 Image Resolution and Quality

One of the biggest challenges in LIST is the limitation of image resolution and quality. Since lensless systems rely on diffraction patterns captured directly by a sensor, the resolution is limited by the pixel size of the sensor and the wavelength of the light source. Although computational algorithms such as pixel super-resolution and phase recovery have improved image quality, a gap remains compared to conventional microscopy. Bishara et al. pointed out the need for improved algorithms to achieve super-resolution imaging.^[92] Future developments could focus on improving imaging speed and user-friendliness.

5.1.2 Computational Complexity

Reconstructing images from diffraction patterns requires complex algorithms, including Fourier transforms and phase recovery, which require significant processing power and can be time-consuming. This complexity is a challenge for POC applications where fast results are critical. The development of faster algorithms is essential for practical real-time applications. Rivenson et al. found that deep learning can reduce computation time while preserving image quality, but further refinements are needed.^[93]

5.1.3 Sensitivity to Environmental Conditions

LIST systems are sensitive to environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and vibration. These factors can destabilize the light source, the sample, or the image sensor and cause artifacts in the captured images. Ensuring consistent imaging performance under variable environmental conditions is challenging in field applications. More robust designs are required to ensure reliable operation under different conditions, but this remains an ongoing challenge.

5.1.4 Sample Preparation and Alignment

Precise sample preparation and alignment are crucial for accurate lensless imaging. Even minor deviations in the alignment of the sample with respect to the light source and sensor can lead to errors in the diffraction patterns and thus affect the reconstructed images. Ensuring accurate positioning, especially in high-throughput or automated systems, is a challenge that needs to be addressed to improve reproducibility. Zhu et al. emphasized the importance of developing standardized sample preparation protocols to minimize variability and improve reproducibility.^[162,210]

5.1.5 Integration with Other Technologies

While LIST offers many advantages, its integration with other diagnostic technologies, such as microfluidics, biosensors, and ML, poses an additional challenge. Successful integration requires careful consideration of these technologies' compatibility in sample handling, data processing, and overall system design. For example, combining lensless imaging with microfluidic chips for POC diagnostics requires precise fluid control, alignment, and real-time data analysis capabilities.

5.2. Future Directions in LIST

5.2.1 Advancements in Computational Imaging

A promising direction for LIST is the continued development of advanced computational imaging techniques. Integrating ML and AI algorithms can significantly improve image reconstruction, increase resolution, and reduce computation time. AI-based approaches can facilitate the automated analysis of complex diffraction patterns and make lensless imaging accessible to non-experts.^[198] Rosen et al. discussed the role of machine learning in advancing computational imaging and suggested that traditional signal processing algorithms can be integrated into more comprehensive machine learning systems to improve performance.^[183]

5.2.2. FOV and DOF Enhancements

Future research could focus on further optimizing the trade-offs between hardware simplifications and AI compensations. This includes developing more advanced deep learning models to handle the reconstruction of compromised data better, ultimately leading to better FOV and DOF in biophotonic imaging.^[182]

5.2.3 Multi-Modal Imaging

Another exciting direction for LIST is the development of multimodal imaging systems that combine lensless imaging with other diagnostic techniques such as fluorescence imaging, Raman spectroscopy, or electrical impedance measurements. These systems can provide complementary information about a sample, leading to a more accurate and comprehensive diagnosis. For example, the combination of lensless imaging with fluorescence could enable the detection of both morphological features and specific molecular markers, improving the system's diagnostic capabilities.

5.2.4. Real-Time Monitoring and POC Applications

The advancement of LISTs holds significant potential for their use in real-time monitoring and POC applications. The ability to provide instant on-the-spot diagnostic results could greatly benefit areas such as infectious disease detection, cancer screening, and environmental

monitoring. Future developments will likely focus on improving the speed and reliability of lensless imaging systems to meet the demands of real-time diagnostics.

6. Conclusion

Recent developments in LIST-based biosensors have significantly improved on-site detection and POC diagnostics. By leveraging the inherent advantages of lensless imaging—such as wide FOV, portability, and cost-effectiveness — innovative biosensor platforms have emerged that are easily accessible and capable of detecting a wide range of biomarkers and pathogens. These advances are significant in resource-constrained environments where traditional diagnostic tools can be impractical. LIST-based biosensors promise to revolutionize POC diagnostics by making advanced medical testing more accessible and affordable worldwide. However, overcoming the remaining challenges in terms of image resolution, computational complexity, and environmental sensitivity is crucial. A strategic combination of technological innovation, collaboration with regulators, and market positioning will be required to overcome these barriers and achieve widespread adoption. The potential impact of these devices on healthcare, particularly on early and accurate disease detection, underlines the importance of continued research and development in this area.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the Basic Science Research Program of the National Research Foundation (NRF) of Korea (Grant#: RS-2024-00353675), the ITRC (Information Technology Research Center) support program supervised by the IITP (Institute for Information and Communications Technology Planning and Evaluation) and funded by the Ministry of Science and ICT (MSIT), Korea (Grant#: IITP-2024-RS-2023-00258971), the Korea Institute of Marine Science and Technology Promotion (KIMST) support program funded by the Ministry of Oceans and Fisheries, Korea (Grant#:20210660), and a Korea University Grant.

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